

Trust is the glue of society - but so is distrust

"Distrust and caution are the parents of security" Benjamin Franklin

If trust is considered the glue of society, then distrust acts like a carving chisel, destabilizing existing relationships and causing even a strong social foundation to gradually crumble. Obviously, our information age with its post-factual tendencies seems to promote the reinforcement of drivers of a culture of distrust and thus the establishment of an "ecosystem of distrust" (Verstraete & Bambauer, 2017) with numerous, frequently discussed negative side effects (Fairbrother, 2017).

This seems plausible at first, but a differentiated view of distrust shows that a purely negative conceptualization may fall short. Thus, the philosopher Lichtenberg already stated in his 1776 that "True unaffected distrust of human powers in all pieces is the surest sign of strength of mind" (Lichtenberg, 1968, p. 506). Furthermore, distrust - as described in the quote from Benjamin Franklin mentioned at the beginning of this article - can also be understood as a sensible security measure. Major theorists of democracy, such as Montesquieu and Constant, argued that there must be institutional barriers to the exercise of power to prevent particular interests from prevailing (Warren, 2017). Similarly, evolution-theoretically oriented scholars argue that it makes sense not to trust blindly to avoid being exploited. Cosmides et al. (2005) therefore emphasize the human predisposition for a sophisticated form of (social) cheat detection. It is supposed to prevent us - but also our fellow human beings - from disadvantageous interactions and protects us and our environment from unwanted free riders and cheaters. It has not been finally clarified whether this specific form of social consciousness is to be regarded because of distrust or whether another construct is better suited to explain this situation.

Consequently, the ambiguous role and the high relevance attributed to distrust requires clarity regarding its relevance, impact, and dynamics. In a first conceptual effort, the approach of Lewicki et al. (1998) has proven to be a concise and interdisciplinary applicable definition. They describe distrust as persuasive, negative expectations related to the behavior of another actor. Bijlsma-Frankema et al. (2015) offer an even more comprehensive definition by additionally highlighting the unwillingness to accept vulnerability, based on perceptions of the other's motives, intentions, and behaviors. Thus, distrust can be described as beliefs of social actors that other social actors would behave adversely to their interests in an interaction. Social actors can also be understood as institutions such as organizations or administrations. Distrust beliefs are based, among other things, on attributing various properties to others, which are combined into a judgment of their unreliability in terms of their abilities and integrity, as well as their benevolence (McKnight & Chervany, 2001).

In this paper, we present current findings on the effects of distrust, especially social distrust, and how distrust relates to trust. We take an interdisciplinary approach to distrust to show its many facets. This consideration is to be understood against the background that a conceptual and empirical engagement with the construct of distrust has only recently gained importance in many disciplines. While trust is considered an established topic area, numerous fundamental questions, such as the causes, preconditions, dimensions, and operationalizations of distrust, are still the subject of current discussions (Guo, Lumineau, & Lewicki, 2017; Sitkin & Bijlsma-Frankema, 2018).

We see the relevance for this overview in the fact that the body of evidence remains very fragmented and only a few papers offer an interdisciplinary overview. This is particularly surprising because distrust has been an accompanying phenomenon to trust for centuries. Based on the current literature, we argue for an autonomous view of distrust. However, this also means that efforts in areas such as measurement (e.g. Rusk, 2018) and possible positive interactions still need to be significantly developed. Overall, we argue to focus on the autonomy of distrust as a social construct. This means that we understand distrust (analogous to Model 3 in Guo et al., 2017, p.26ff) as an independent construct with its own dimensions in relation to trust. In this sense, for instance a mere consideration of the dark side of trust (Gargiulo & Ertug, 2006) also falls short.

Through this paper, we would like to show how an autonomous analysis of distrust can be achieved. This is to be understood considering the assumption that numerous social institutions (e.g., the peer review process or data transparency in science) function well precisely because they are met with a certain degree of distrust. In this sense, it can be said that trust is the glue of society - but so is (surprisingly) distrust.

Literature

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